

Workshop - Learning programming with Generative AI: Hands-On Exploration and Ethical Reflection

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15918309>

Abstract

What if every student had a tireless, patient coding tutor? Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) makes this possible—but at what cost? GenAI has rapidly evolved into a versatile tool for tasks ranging from creative writing to problem-solving, with programming being one of its most transformative applications. These models offer not only solutions and inspiration but also instant, iterative feedback—making them powerful allies for skill acquisition. In this workshop, participants (with or without prior programming experience) will actively engage with GenAI to Experience AI-assisted programming first-hand; discuss techno-ethical implications (e.g., over-reliance, plagiarism, bias) and explore strategies to integrate these tools effectively into education while preserving deep learning.

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; Generative AI. Computing Methodologies

1 Introduction

Generative AI (GenAI) refers to a class of artificial intelligence models capable of producing text, code, images, and other forms of media in response to user prompts. Tools like OpenAI's ChatGPT¹¹, Google's Gemini¹², DeepSeek¹³ and GitHub Copilot¹⁴ are trained on extensive datasets and are able to generate highly coherent, human-like outputs. These capabilities make GenAI valuable for a wide range of tasks, including content creation, problem-solving, and decision-making. By enabling users to quickly draft documents, improve written work, and access information effortlessly, these tools are reshaping productivity and how we work and learn.

In educational settings, GenAI functions as an endlessly patient and always-available tutor. It delivers explanations adapted to individual learners' levels, assists in brainstorming, and offers real-time feedback—supporting a highly personalized and self-directed learning experience. Therefore, in recent years, artificial intelligence (AI) has attracted increasing interest within the education sector, as more institutions and organizations explore the potential of AI-driven technologies to enhance learning (Dwivedi et al., 2021; Su & Yang, (2023); Noroozi et al. (2024)).

In engineering education, students have quickly embraced GenAI tools, especially those geared toward programming (Becker (2023)). A growing ecosystem of platforms provides features like code generation, debugging assistance, and natural language explanations of technical concepts. These tools are transforming how students engage with programming, often surpassing traditional methods that rely on static documentation, textbooks, or delayed instructor feedback (Yilmaz et al. (2023)).

¹¹ chat.openai.com

¹² gemini.google.com

¹³ <https://chat.deepseek.com/>

¹⁴ <https://github.com/features/copilot>

The research community views GenAI as a significant and emerging opportunity in education (Alasadi & Baiz (2023)). However, ChatGPT, a cutting-edge natural language processing (NLP) model developed by OpenAI in 2019 (Lund & Wang, (2023)) was only released in late 2022. We are still in the early stages of understanding how to effectively integrate them into academic settings. Questions remain around when, how, and to what extent these tools should be incorporated into coursework and curricula and research around the topic has grown exponentially in the last years (Qadir (2023); Giannakos et al. (2024)). Moreover, while AI can greatly enhance productivity, it also brings challenges—such as the risk of hallucinations (incorrect outputs), over-reliance, frustration when used uncritically, and even the potential to replace meaningful learning rather than support it (Mittal et al. (2024); Sharples (2023)).

These uncertainties and challenges are the motivation for this workshop, which aims to explore these issues and foster thoughtful reflection on how GenAI can be integrated into the classroom in a way that enhances—rather than replaces—the learning experience.

In this workshop, participants will actively engage with GenAI tools—such as ChatGPT, GitHub Copilot, and cloud-based Python environments—to support their learning of Python programming. They will experience AI-assisted programming firsthand through activities like code generation, debugging, and project ideation. After exploring both the potential and limitations of these tools, we will open the floor for discussion. Debate will be focused on: (i) critical reflections on concerns and techno-ethical implications, such as over-reliance on AI, plagiarism, and algorithmic bias; and (ii) strategies for meaningfully integrating these tools into educational contexts to enrich and enhance student learning. This workshop paper mainly targets the Conference theme of Artificial Intelligence and digital technologies, its ethical implications are also considered.

2 Activities

In this hands-on session, participants will take part in an AI-assisted programming workshop, followed by a group reflection and an open debate on ethical considerations and best practices. Working in teams, participants will need one laptop per group. The session is designed to provide practical experience with GenAI tools while fostering thoughtful discussion on their use in education. The session is structured as follows:

- **Introduction:** We'll begin with a quick interactive poll: "Have you used AI for coding before?" Followed by a brief overview of GenAI tools with a focus on programming.
- **Team-based AI-assisted coding experience:** Participants will work in teams using AI assistants (e.g., ChatGPT, GitHub Copilot) and no-setup, cloud-based IDEs (e.g., Replit15, Google Colab). Each team will tackle a set of challenges:
 - Code Understanding: Analyze a provided Python program with the help of AI.
 - Code Generation: Prompt the AI to write a basic program (e.g., reversing a string), then adapt or expand it.
 - Debugging: Introduce errors into working code and use AI to identify and fix them.
 - Mini-Project: Collaborate with AI to build a small custom project (e.g., a to-do list app).
- **Group Reflections & Presentations:** Each team will share their project and first impressions of the experience. Sample questions: "What surprised you the most?" "Was the AI easy to use?" "Where did you find limitations?"

¹⁵ replit.com

- **Ethical Considerations & Best Practices (Open Debate):** We'll explore the challenges of using AI in learning environments. Debate will be aimed at identifying potential risks—such as blind reliance on AI, reduced problem-solving effort, or plagiarism—and propose best practices. For example: Verify AI suggestions with official documentation, use AI as a brainstorming partner, not a final answer key, reinforce fundamentals through manual coding practice.

Inspirational Questions to Spark Debate:

- Should AI-generated code be allowed in coding exams?
- How can educators integrate AI tools without diminishing learning outcomes?
- How should learning outcomes change when introducing AI tools?
- Does AI encourage creativity or discourage original thinking?
- What skills become more important in an AI-assisted world?
- Can AI help level the playing field for students with different motivations or backgrounds?
- Should students be taught how to “talk to AI” effectively?

3 Expected results

Through hands-on activities and guided discussion, participants will leave with:

- A practical understanding of GenAI's capabilities and limitations in the context of programming.
- Actionable strategies for using AI to enhance—rather than replace—the learning process.
- A critical perspective on the societal and pedagogical implications of GenAI in education.

4 Instructions for Participants

This activity is open to anyone with an interest in the topic. No prior experience with programming or AI tools is required to participate in the workshop. Participants are required to bring a laptop, otherwise a computer per team should be made available to ensure everyone can fully engage in the session.

5 Conclusions and Take-aways

Generative AI is reshaping programming education by providing instant support, personalized feedback, and creative inspiration. However, its effectiveness depends on mindful usage—balancing AI assistance with active problem-solving. Participants will leave with:

- Hands-on experience using AI for coding tasks.
- Frameworks for responsible use in educational settings.
- Awareness of ethical and pedagogical challenges.
- Strategies to integrate AI as a learning enhancer, not a crutch.

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